

positions 5, 6, 7, 8 of 2-naphthalene ring), 7.55–7.6 (2H, aromatic and in the vicinity of NHN), 7.75 (1H, aromatic and at position-4 of 2-naphthalene ring), 7.80–7.85 (2H, aromatic and at positions 1 and 3 of the 2-naphthalene ring), 8.29 (1H, NHN), and 9.25 (1H, CONH).

The physical data of the pyrazolones are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE PYRAZOLINONES*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃	220	42.15
2.	4-CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃	249	37.47
3.	2-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	245	26.94
4.	4-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	230	33.48
5.	4-Br	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₃	220	12.19
6.	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄	202	33.86
7.	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄	224	25.58
8.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄	237	33.91
9.	4-NO ₂	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₅	227	26.92

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The pyrazolinones were examined for their dyeing characteristics on wool, cotton and polyester using two different mordants, namely chromium sulphate (for wool) and copper sulphate (for cotton and polyester). The pyrazolinones imparted beautiful shades of light yellow to orange on these fibres. Investigations showed that the colours produced are fast to light and soap.

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Fragrant Volatiles in Rice and Marking Fluid of Tiger

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THE marking fluid (MF) of the tiger ejected upwards through the urinary channel but distinct from urine, is believed to be the source of semiochemicals, i.e. pheromones, which serve to mark territory and to invite the opposite sex¹⁻⁴.

The study of the chemical nature of the volatiles in the MF, the likely candidates for pheromones, was initiated earlier^{2,3}. This is associated with the science of smell, a formidable subject for the chemists, because a very few molecules, sometimes a single one, can be perceived by an animal. Since 1986 we have been studying such molecules of smell in the MF of several adult tigers and in the urine of two cub tigers at Nandan Kanan open-air zoo, Orissa. The MF from adult tigers was collected by a procedure developed over the last ten years, based on certain behavioural properties of tigers. MF has a characteristic pleasant aroma, partly masked by ammonia and other constituents. The adult urine, but not the urine of the cub, contains the same aroma. Under the best conditions this aroma is surprisingly close to the fragrant Indian rice varieties. Only 8% of fragrance in cooked rice has recently been elucidated to be 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline⁵ and the major part of aroma of cooked and uncooked rice is still unknown.

The fragrant material could be extracted from MF by chloroform, diethyl ether, hexane or heptane. When these extracts or the steam distillate of MF were shaken with 1 N HCl, the aroma disappeared. When these aqueous acid extracts were rendered alkaline with 1 N NaOH solution, the aroma reappeared (The rice aroma also exhibited these very properties). This behaviour of the fragrant material from the tiger suggested that it might be an organic base, rather like the rice aroma.

We have therefore carried out a comparative study of the retention-characteristics of these two compounds in both paper chromatography (pc) and gas-liquid chromatography (glc) in order to find out whether these molecules are identical from the stand-point of retention characteristics.

Following our earlier work^{2,3}, a thorough search was made to isolate the aroma-substance with the help of pc. Acidified steam-distillate or the supernatant after centrifugation of acidified MF was spotted on Whatman 3M paper strips and developed up to ~17 cm with a solvent mixture of n-butanol,

acetic acid and water (4:1:1, v/v). The chromatograms were air-dried to remove the solvent and cut into consecutive horizontal strips. Each such strip was rendered alkaline with dilute NaOH solution. Within a few seconds the distinct rice like aroma appeared in the strips corresponding to a specific region of the chromatogram, well-separated from ninhydrin-positive spots due to putrescine, cadaverine and phenylethylamine of MF under similar chromatographic conditions. The acidified steam-distillates of MF and rice were spotted and developed side by side on a chromatogram under the same previous conditions. The two aroma regions (MF and rice) coincide and both are ninhydrin-negative.

The 'head space' analysis of MF or its chloroform or hexane or heptane extract was carried out with the help of a Hewlett Packard 5840A dual column analytical gas chromatograph with FID detectors.

MF or chloroform extracts (~2 ml) were taken in screw capped septum vials (3.5 ml) with butyl rubber septum (Pierce, USA) and kept at 30° for 30 min. The 'head space' gas (1 ml), that is the gas above the liquid, was injected into the column and chromatographed using nitrogen as carrier gas. Different samples of MF of two tiggesses and one tiger were used in different seasons. In case of rice, about half of such septum vial was filled with rice, well-moistened with distilled water and kept at 30° for 1 h. The head-space (1 ml) was injected and chromatographed as above. In this way comparison of the glc retention characteristics of the two aroma substances could be made under the same conditions.

The columns chosen for glc analysis were 10% squalane on chromosorb W(HP) (100-12) mesh) and 10% carbowax 20M on chromosorb W(HP) (100-120 mesh) respectively, packed in stainless steel columns (3 m × 3 mm id). Chromatograms were taken at 45° for squalane, and 60° for carbowax columns. The injection port and FID temperature were kept at 20° above column temperature. The carrier gas flow rate was kept at 30 ml min⁻¹. Both MF-head-space and rice-head-space produced one major peak at the identical t_R of 4.8 min on squalane column and a sharper major peak at t_R 2.3 min on carbowax 20M column. Injection of a mixture of the two head-spaces (MF and rice) on the carbowax 20M column resulted in a single peak of t_R 2.3 min. Moreover, injection of head-space of old MF and rice water which have lost the aroma, did not show any such peak.

It thus seems that the fragrant substance in MF is likely to be an organic base which is shared by fragrant varieties of rice.

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Chemical Examination of a Marine Zoanthid of *Gemmaria* sp.

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IN continuation of our study on toxic marine organisms of Visakhapatnam coast^{1,2}, chemical examination of an unidentified *Gemmaria* sp. (Phylum: Coelenterata) is reported here. These animals grow as mats on the intertidal rocks of the Visakhapatnam coast (N 17°, E 83°) and they have a cylindrical structure with a folded bulb-like opening. The animals are attached to the rocky substratum through calcareous matter. The animals (after washing with water) were extracted with aqueous alcohol and subsequent chromatography furnished two compounds A and B.

Compound A analysed for C₂₈H₄₈O, showed the characteristic LB test for sterols. It was found to be transparent in uv (MeOH) and showed ir (KBr) absorption at 3 500 cm⁻¹(OH). It formed a non-acetate (1a) (Ac₂O/Py), C₃₀H₅₀O₂, M⁺ 442, m.p. 133-34°, [α]_D -31.06°; R_f 0.75 (benzene). A comparative study of the ¹H nmr spectra (90 MHz, CDCl₃) of the compound at δ 5.4 (1H, m, C₂-H), 3.43 (1H, m, C₃-H), 1.02 (3H, s, C₁₀-Me), 0.74-0.95 (9H, m, 21, 26 and 27-Me) and 0.7 (3H, s, C₁₄-Me); and its acetate at δ (270 MHz, CDCl₃), 5.38 (1H, m, C₂-H), 4.59 (1H, m, C₃-H), 2.03 (3H, s, C₈-OCOCH₃), 1.02 (3H, s, 19-Me), 0.92 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 21-Me), 0.86 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 26-CH₃), 0.78 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 27-CH₃), 0.78 (3H, d, J 7 Hz,